

KINEMATIC ANALYSIS OF GAIT PERFORMANCE & TRUNK BENDING IN STROKE PATIENTS: A RANDOMIZED CONTROL TRIAL

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Abstract

Background: The role of trunk muscles in healthy as well as in the hemiplegic patients is vital & can't be denied. This study is based on the analysis of trunk, which is defined for this study as follow; the ability of the trunk to keep body up right against gravity during movements & as well as to find out the correlation between trunk functions & gait performance

Method: 20 study participants (10 hemiplegic & 10 healthy adults, Male, n=20, female, n=0) trunk functions were assessed by 3D motion analysis system. The musculature of the trunk was divided into; a) pelvis b) middle trunk c) upper trunk. The trunk analysis was based on clinical parameters, including; a) static standing b) in standing position anterior tilt of the trunk c) gait performance. The trunk functions relationship with the performance of gait was also assessed. The data was analysed on SPSS V. 23 with the P-value >0.005.

Results: the comparative data analysis of the study shows that during trunk bending greater angular rotation was found towards the non-involved side & middle trunk rotates towards the involved side at the time of toe off the involved limb in hemiplegic patient during gait. It has been observed that the degree of rotation was correlated with gait performance of the study subject.

Conclusion; The result of the study can be concluded that middle trunk movements affect gait performance in hemiplegic patients. It has also been observed that gravity & lower limb movements considerably affected the function s of middle trunk in hemiplegic patients.

Introduction:

Stroke is the 3rd cause of death globally; from 1990-2007 age standardized year of life lost (YLL) increased by 12.9% (10.6-15.2) & from 2007-2017 by 12.1%, while the stroke incidence

increased 5.29Million (5.22-5.40) to 6.17 million (6.4-6.33) from 2007-2017, thus, it increased DALYs (disability adjusted life years) due to multifaceted morbidity & effects of longevity from 3.54 to 9.66% in the period

1990-2013 as reported GBD statistic (Global burden of the Diseases)². High income countries (HIC) recorded a 42% decrease in the stroke while on the other hand low- & middle-income countries (LMIC) showed 100% increase in the last 3-4 decades³. The statistics records that there are around 62 million stroke survivors globally while 1/3rd among them is living with severe disabilities⁴. It has been estimated that more than 80% DALYs occurs in LMIC^{5,6}. In spite of the recent effective advancement made in the management of the stroke such as; thrombolytic & endovascular interventions stroke remains one of the most common cause of disability worldwide^{7,8}. Post-stroke disability is still a major health burden⁸. There is variation in the rehabilitation programs provided to the stroke patients worldwide & the quality & content of the program depends mostly on the medical & financial resources^{9,10}. The role of trunk muscles in the healthy as well as in the hemiplegic patients is vital & can't be denied. This study is based on the analysis of trunk, which is defined for this study as follow; the ability of the trunk to keep body up right against gravity during movements & as well as to find out the correlation between trunk functions & gait performance. For the social re-integration of the hemiplegic patients the improvement in the ADLs or the hemiplegic patient ability to perform ADLs is essential. In order to perform ADLs effectively in the social circuit functions of trunk & lower extremities are vital for the hemiplegic patient^{11,12}. It has been observed that during the gait the mandatory functions of lower limb are a) forward propulsion b) the ability to maintain body upright c) energy conservation d) shock absorption². Due to chronic synergy development & abnormal tonality the functions of the lower extremities don't perform their functions in the hemiplegic patients. Abnormal tonality & active synergy in the hemiplegic patient's lower extremities leads to reduced gait speed, imbalance, falls & the patient become independent¹¹⁻¹³. The methods of evaluation for the lower extremities function used across the world are a) Fugl-Meyer assessment (FMA) b) Brunnstrom recovery stage

(BRS) c) Manual Muscle tests (MMT). These methods or outcome measure don't evaluate the trunk functions or its role in gait performance parameters in the hemiplegic patients. It has been reported that trunk functions such as; trunk muscle strength, coordination, flexibility & endurance are strongly correlated with the gait performance in the hemiplegic patients. Trunk functions are evaluated by a) Trunk impairment scale^{14,15} (TIS) b) Trunk control test^{16,17} c) functional assessment for the control of trunk ²⁵. The limitation of these outcome measures is its inability to locate the causative factors for the patient's poor performance, however, it locate & indentify hemiplegic patients poor trunk functions accurately.

Trunk has been termed^{18,19} as " Passenger unit" in the literature as it has been ambulated & carried out by the lower extremities²¹. In the normal & healthy individuals, the muscles of neck & trunk are sufficient enough to maintain trunk in the upright & neutral position. thus, it has been linked strongly with the performance of gait & ADLs in the hemiplegic patients ⁸⁻¹⁰. It has been reported that trunk training in the hemiplegic patients improves gait parameters & body balance (both static & dynamic). In order to clarified further, this study was to designed to find out the role of trunk muscles functions in the hemiplegic patient gait performance.

It has been reported that improvement in the patient performance in ADLs is comparatively more easily gained than the gait performance in the hemiplegic populations. The trunk role in ADLs performance is essential as moving from sitting to standing & performing various functions it would be impossible without the intact trunk functions. During bending the trunk ROM is maintained by erector spinae muscles & there is an essential needs for the coordination of erector spinae, Multifidus, lumborum & transverse abdomens of the lower trunk muscles^{8,9}. The activities of these trunk muscles are comparatively more important in gait than in the static trunk posture as the force of gravity increase with body's posture alteration. During gait, it is highly important to

maintain upright trunk posture, which can't be achieved without the coordinated efforts of the trunk muscles. It has been reported that the loss of selective activity of trunk musculature leads to the inability of the thoracic optimal extension in gait while the whole force is shifted to the lower abdominals [11,20,21].

The outcome measures used by studies for the performance of in the hemiplegic patients are a) ground reaction forces b) gait abnormality rating scale c) Wiscinsin gait scale d) gait speed. For the independence walking a speed at the certain range is required, thus, for the conduction of this study, we decided trunk bending as a means of investigating the hemiplegic patient's ability to support their trunk in the upright posture during the gait & gait speed as performance parameters.

The aim of this study to investigate & observe trunk functions on 3D motions analysis systems in the King hospital, physical therapy department & to find out the relationships of trunk functions & gait performance in the hemiplegic patients. Trunk functions is defined (operational definition) as "the individual ability

to maintain trunk in the upright posture during forward bending in gait".

Methodology:

20 study participants (10 hemiplegic & 10 healthy adults) trunk functions were assessed by 3D motion analysis system. The musculature of the trunk was divided into; a) pelvis b) middle trunk c) upper trunk. The trunk analysis was based on clinical parameters, including; a) static standing b) in standing position anterior tilt of the trunk c) gait performance. The trunk functions relationship with the performance of gait was also assessed. The data was analysed on SPSS V. 23 with the P-value >0.005. All the study participants could stand for 10s independently. The control group (CG) contained adult healthy individuals having no orthopaedic, neurological or neuromuscular conditions & able to perform easily ADLs. TIS was used for the evaluation of trunk functions in the hemiplegic patients while FMA was used the sensory & motor functions evaluation of the lower extremities & functional independence measure was used to asses study's subject's functional level. The demographic of the study participants is given below in Table-1.

Table-1: Study's Participants demographics (P-value; >0.001)

Characteristics	Hemiplegic patients n=10	Healthy adults n=10
Age	78.2±2.3	55.3±8.3
Height (mm)	164.2±46.3	163.3±45.2
Weight (Kg)	62.2±13.2	63.2±12.5

Table-2: Hemiplegic Study's Participants general Characteristics

Characteristics	Values
Time since onset	106.3 ± 34.3
Stroke type	Cerebral infarction n=4, cerebral haemorrhage n=6
Involved side	Right, n=5, Left, n=5

For the study measurement two labs were used for individuals' motions & posture, which includes; a) 3D motion analysis system; Vicon Nexus, UK b) AMTI-USA 6-force plate or its variants. Gait, trunk bending & static standing of the study's participants were measured at rate of 100-120Hz. Sensitive markers of the motion

analysis systems were attached to the acromion process, coracoids process, anterior superior iliac spine (ASIS), posterior superior iliac spine (PSIS), greater trochanter, knee joints, 5th metatarsal bones, suprasternal notch, lateral malleolus, 2nd thoracic spine process, xiphoid process, T8 & T10. Before the recordable measurement was

made, study's participants practiced several times with the measuring of the devices systems. The study's participants were briefed & demonstrated the whole procedure. For static standing the study's participants was instructed to look straight ahead, relaxed but instructions regarding their feet placements or the direction it needs to be in position was not given. The ground reaction force (GRF) was recorded for 10s for each study's participants after confirming the system is working properly. The study's participants were instructed to bend 30° & maintain it for 3-4s to record the measurement of the trunk bending. Each participant repeated bending 4 times & the best score was recorded for the study analysis. The range of bending further was the subject's subjective decision & neither instructions nor encouragement cues were given during the trunk bending. For the measurement of the study's participants gait performance, the subjects were asked to walk comfortably on the designated path at the physical therapy department of the hospital. Assistive devices use was allowed for the subjects in order to avoid falls. 5 cycles of walking dominant side data of the healthy study's participants were obtained & data for the involved side of the hemiplegic subjects were obtained.

Operational definition for the study used are as follow; a) upper trunk segment; markers of coracoids process, 2nd thoracic spine process & suprasternal notch. B) Pelvis segment; markers on ASIS & PSIS. C) Middle trunk segment; a straight imaginary line between xiphoid process & T8. The angle of forward rotation of the 3 segments of trunk with respect to the coordinates of the lab system were measured & recorded. D) Positive value denoted forward tilt & rotation to the non-dominant side in the healthy study's subjects while rotation to the non-affected side in the hemiplegic study's subjects. E) Average angle & GRF for 3-5s in standing for the study's subjects were recorded before the conduction of the study. F) The starting position for trunk bending was defined as "the position in which the suprasternal notch was its minimum forward points at the sagittal plane" G) The maximum

position for trunk bending was defined as "the position in which the suprasternal notch was its maximum forward points at the sagittal plane". For each part of the trunk measurement (best score of 5 attempts) the angles during trunk motions were recorded as the changes from the starting static position. For the measurement of gait performance in study's subjects the same trunk parameters was used.

For the analysis of data SPSS V.23 was used. Mann-Whitney U- test was applied to find out the difference between groups; healthy vs. hemiplegic subjects while spearman correlation coefficients were used to find the relationship between trunk bending & gait performance. Descriptive statistic was applied for the study demographic variables.

Results; the comparative data analysis of the study shows that during trunk bending greater angular rotation was found towards the non-involved side & middle trunk rotates towards the involved side at the time of toe off the involved limb in hemiplegic patient during gait. It has been observed that the degree of rotation was correlated with gait performance of the study subject. The result of the study can be concluded that middle trunk movements affect gait performance in hemiplegic patients. It has also been observed that gravity & lower limb movements considerably affected the function s of middle trunk in hemiplegic patients. The FMA & TIS results is given below in Table-3.

Gait speed in the healthy study subjects was 0.88 ± 0.24 m/s & 0.58 ± 0.44 m/s in hemiplegic patients. In static standing the middle trunk forward tilt were considerably differed among healthy & hemiplegic study subjects. The vertical GRF was 46 ± 3.4 % on the non-dominant side of healthy study's subjects & 58 ± 4.5 % on the non-involved side of the hemiplegic study's subjects.

Various differences were observed between the groups for the trunk bending category. In contrast to the rotation angle, the tilt angles in the hemiplegic patients of the 3 parts were smaller than the healthy individuals. (Table-4), however, the vertical component of GRF during trunk bending its fluctuation wasn't observed

from the values observed in static standing for both groups.

At the gait performance, it was observed that at IC the pelvis forward tilt angle & middle trunk was smaller in healthy subjects than in the hemiplegic patients, while at the TO, the rotation angle of trunk differs considerably between the two groups. (Table-5).

This study observed negative relationship between gait speed & rotation angle of the middle trunk & a positive relationship between gait speed & rotation angle of the middle trunk at TO of the involved side in the hemiplegic study's subjects. (Table-6).

Table-3: Hemiplegic study's subjects' clinical data

Test applied	Values
FIM score	107.3 ± 14.4
Motor-Fugal-Meyer score	26.4±7.6
Sensory- Fugal-Meyer score	8.3±3.4
TIS score	14.5±5.6
In-hospital ambulatory means	5 gait + 5 wheelchairs & other assistive devices

In static standing of the study's participants middle trunk-forward tilt was considerably differed between hemiplegic study's subjects & healthy adults.

Table -4: Rotation angle of the trunk during bending & Tilt (P-value; >0.05)

Clinical parameters	Targeted trunk segments	Healthy adults	Hemiplegic patients
Tilt angle	Upper trunk	48.3±8.2 ⁰	42.3±8.2 ⁰
	Lower trunk	43.6±7.2 ⁰	40.3±6.4 ⁰
	Pelvis	28.3±8.2 ⁰	19.3±5.2 ⁰
Rotation angle	Upper trunk	1.3±1.9 ⁰	2.3±4.2 ⁰
	Lower trunk	0.8±1.2 ⁰	4.8±6.2 ⁰
	Pelvis	1.8±2.2 ⁰	2.1±4.2 ⁰

Table-5: Rotation angle of the trunk during bending & Tilt P-value; >0.05-.01)

Side & gait phase	Parameters	Healthy adults' participants (n=10)	Hemiplegic participants (n=10)
R-affected side IC	Upper trunk tilt angle	4.8±4.2 ⁰	3.8±4.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk tilt angle	3.8±2.2 ⁰	1.4±2.9 ⁰
	Pelvis tilt angle	.4±2.5 ⁰	-4.6±5.2 ⁰
	Upper trunk rotation angle	-.8±3.2 ⁰	-2.8±5.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk rotation angle	.8±3.5 ⁰	-1.5±2.2 ⁰
	Pelvis rotation angle	1.8±2.2 ⁰	1.8±2.2 ⁰
L-non-involved side/TO	Upper trunk tilt angle	4.8±4.2 ⁰	3.8±5.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk tilt angle	2.8±3.8 ⁰	2.8±3.2 ⁰
	Pelvis tilt angle	-.8±3.8 ⁰	1.8±2.2 ⁰
	Upper trunk rotation angle	.2±2.3 ⁰	-2.8±4.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk rotation	.8±2.9 ⁰	-1.5±4.2 ⁰

	angle		
	Pelvis rotation angle	4.4±3.4 ⁰	1.8±4.2 ⁰
L-non-involved side - IC	Upper trunk tilt angle	5.8±4.2 ⁰	5.8±7.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk tilt angle	3.8±3.2 ⁰	5.8±4.2 ⁰
	Pelvis tilt angle	1.3±2.2 ⁰	1.8±2.2 ⁰
	Upper trunk rotation angle	1.8±2.2 ⁰	4.8±4.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk rotation angle	2.4±3.2 ⁰	.8±3.6 ⁰
	Pelvis rotation angle	2.8±3.5 ⁰	2.8±2.2 ⁰
R-involved side -TO	Upper trunk tilt angle	3.8±4.2 ⁰	5.8±5.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk tilt angle	2.8±3.2 ⁰	.4±4.2 ⁰
	Pelvis tilt angle	-.8±2.2 ⁰	1.8±2.2 ⁰
	Upper trunk rotation angle	1.8±2.2 ⁰	-3.8±2.2 ⁰
	Middle trunk rotation angle	1.8±2.2 ⁰	-4.8±2.2 ⁰
	Pelvis rotation angle	-1.8±3.2 ⁰	-4.8±2.2 ⁰

Table-6: Relationship between rotation & tilt of trunk & gait speed (P-value; >0.05)

Movement	Clinical parameters	Healthy subjects	Hemiplegic subjects
Trunk bending	Upper trunk tilt angle	0.04	0.33
	Middle trunk tilt angle	0.04	0.21
	Pelvis tilt angle	0.43	-0.5
	Upper trunk rotation	-0.34	-0.47
	Middle trunk rotation	-0.13	-0.56
Gait	Middle trunk tilt angle (IC)	0.05	0.45
	Pelvis tilt angle (IC)	0.42	-0.05
	Upper trunk rotation (TO)	0.16	0.30
	Middle trunk rotation (TO)	0.18	0.57

Note; 1) Negative correlation indicates that larger rotation of the middle trunk bend towards the affected side was correlated with reduced gait speed among the study subjects. 2) Positive correlation indicates that larger rotation of the middle trunk moves toward the affected side during gait was correlated with slower gait speed among the study subjects. 3) Positive value of the tilt angle shows forward tilt & for healthy subjects' positive value of rotation indicates rotation to the involved side. 4) Positive value of rotation for the hemiplegic patients indicates rotation to the non-involved side.

Discussion; In humans standing is essential for the performance of various ADLs & middle part of the trunk plays a pivotal role in maintain upright & proper posture during various ADLs³⁵. Hemiplegic patients have impaired balance & thus, mostly have inability to perform ADLs effectively & become dependent on others^{18,19}. In this study, we observed that middle trunk was comparatively more tilted forward in hemiplegic's study subjects than the healthy individuals, which is in line with another study⁸. This observation may be explained that due to spastic musculature in the hemiplegic patients around the trunk, the

body become less rigid & more prone to fall forward or low capacity of keep against gravity.

It was observed that degree of forward bending in all parts of the trunk in hemiplegic patients was relatively reduced as compared to the healthy individuals enrolled for the study, which is in line with the findings of a previous study⁴. The capacity of the trunk to extend requires greater anti-extension capacity at the trunk level in gait as compared to static standing. This study also observed that hemiplegic patients have lower capacity for maintaining or sustaining extension at the body ambulation than the static standing, which was again in line & consistent with study's findings^{9,4}, however, these findings differs then the findings of other previous studies^{3,8}.

This study indicated precisely the relationship between middle trunk rotation angle during trunk bending at gait phase TO of the involved side, which is consistent with the findings of a previous study⁴. At TO the trunk is lean forward & placed in front of the involved side & the affected side hip flexes towards the swing phase of the gait from extension in the terminal phase of the gait. The iliopsoas functionality at TO hip flexion of the affected side is vital as it generate a force in the clear the ground in the eccentric contraction of the lower limbs²⁹ & at the IC the stored force is released, while at TO, the muscle shortens & pulls the trunk forward & downward in the healthy individuals but iliopsoas is commonly shortens in hemiplegic patients & unable to extend at the late stance of the gait, which pushes pelvis & trunk to move closer to the femur at TO or stance phase. Along with shortens iliopsoas, ROM at ankle & hip plays also a role in the reduction of gait in hemiplegic patients.

Limitations; 1) Due to lack of EMG activity of the trunk muscle as unit or single muscle at the time of ambulation & gait could not be determined 2) This study focused on the trunk bending & excluded the role of the involved limb. 3) Only men were enrolled due to 3D analysis on parts of the body, which is ethically not allowed as per culture norm for women 4) small sample size.

Conclusion; the comparative data analysis of the study shows that during trunk bending greater angular rotation was found towards the non-involved side & middle trunk rotates towards the involved side at the time of toe off the involved limb in hemiplegic patient during gait. It has been observed that the degree of rotation was correlated with gait performance of the study subject. The result of the study can be concluded that middle trunk movements affect gait performance in hemiplegic patients. It has also been observed that gravity & lower limb movements considerably affected the function s of middle trunk in hemiplegic patients.

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